

Schools' Organizational Culture and Principals' Leadership Practices in Relation to the Teachers' Level of Job Satisfaction

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Abstract:- Organizational culture and principal leadership practices play important roles in promoting teachers' commitment and job satisfaction. This study identified the schools' organizational culture and the principals' leadership practices in relation to the teachers' level of job satisfaction in the Division of Zamboanga del Norte during the school year 2019-2020. The researcher used a descriptive-correlational design in the study. Fifty-four school heads and 233 teachers were chosen as respondents through stratified sampling. The researcher used the modified and adapted Organizational Culture Assessment Inventory, Leadership Practices Inventory, and Teacher Job Satisfaction Survey Questionnaire as the instruments. The Mean, Standard Deviation, Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient, and Stepwise Multiple Regression Analysis were used to analyze and interpret the data. Findings revealed that the schools had very good organizational culture and leadership practices, with very high job satisfaction among teachers. The schools' organizational culture regarding dominant characteristics was related to the teachers' job satisfaction in supervision, colleague, working condition, pay factor, and security. The organizational leadership was related to the teachers' security. Organizational glue was related to the teachers' satisfaction with their working conditions and pay. The schools' strategic emphasis were also related to the teachers' satisfaction level on the pay factor. Criteria of success of the organization were related to the satisfaction level of teachers in the areas of a colleague and pay factor. The principal's leadership practices in modeling the way were related to the teachers' job satisfaction regarding pay. The school's culture in the areas of dominant characteristics and organizational leadership; and the principals' leadership practices on encouraging the heart of the teachers were the predictors of teachers' job satisfaction. The school has a very effective organizational culture and leadership practices of principals. How the organization is built and how the principal sets an example to getting things done in the institution greatly affect the teachers' job satisfaction. Future researchers may conduct another research looking into other variables that may affect the satisfaction of teachers.

Keywords: Job Satisfaction, Leadership, Organizational Culture, Principals, Quantitativ.

I. INTRODUCTION

Cultures predict organizational effectiveness. An organization with strong culture performs more effectively than an organization with a weak culture. Organizational culture leadership affects institutional effectiveness through organizational culture management (Gochhayat, Giri, & Suar, 2017). Promoting the teaching culture in schools demanded a school leadership approach. Strategic leadership and organizational productivity were positively related. Principals who practiced strategic leadership promoted teacher commitment (Khumalo, 2018).

The institution's culture contributed to the organization's uniqueness of values, behavior, psychology, experience, ways of thinking, and organizational expectations. Improving employee behavior into organizational citizenship behavior is needed by every organization (Arumi, Aldrin, & Murti, 2019). Organizational culture significantly affected the importance of school policy (Huang & Teo, 2020). The organizational culture and school leadership were influenced by national culture (Ana Maria de & Maria Zélia, 2018).

School culture affects both leadership styles and the corporate image. Leadership styles played a vital role in developing an image of school culture (Kalkan Ümit et al., 2020). Integrating values and leadership values into the institutional vision strengthened the school culture and improved the achievement of school (Imron, Juharyanto, Mustiningsih, & Ahmad, 2018).

Teachers perceived school culture strongly with corporate image. The school culture and corporate image were significantly related to the style of leadership of school administrators. Principals' leadership style predicted significantly the school culture. Then the school culture also predicted corporate image (Kalkan Ümit, Altınay, Ramazan, & Gökmen, 2020). However, the teachers perceived the organizational culture as moderate, and the teachers' occupational stress was low in a school organization (Chan Mya, Ye, & Boonpram, 2017). Thus, the

teachers' perception of organizational culture negatively related with their occupational stress.

Teachers and students built an organizational culture and relational leadership at a public primary school situated in South Australia upon the strength of the inter-relationships. The individual strengths of staff served the formation of organizational life. Cognizant of these disclosed relational underpinnings, the research provided recommendations to the school's leadership team about how they could best progress their educational reform agenda (Giles, & Bills, 2017). Different cultural typologies resulted in varying levels of commitment in the organizations. Culture support had a strong significant relationship with a normative and ongoing commitment. It means that if the organization shows a sense of care and support to its employees, they will develop an obligatory sense of belonging and help the organization attain its objectives (Wiseman, Ngirande, & Sam, 2017).

The success of school-based interventions can be greatly influenced by organizational culture. For example, schools may use data collected on an organizational level to identify strategies for establishing a supportive environment in the school setting (Fair, Solari Williams, Warren, Lisako, & Ory, 2018). In addition, school principals were expected to build an organizational culture to ensure individual capacities in school (Burhanuddin, 2019).

A school quality management culture should be distinct from the school organizational culture. The complex relationship between the leaders' culture and practices was more appropriate than integrated approaches (Markowitsch Jörg, 2018). Perceived usefulness, attitude towards using technology, organizational culture, and teacher perceptions of the importance of school policy on technology use were significant antecedents to teachers' behavior (Huang & Teo, 2020).

Organizational culture contributed directly, , to the performance of new school personnel. Learning organizations promoted insights into new personnel and shared team knowledge (Klein & Shapira-Lishchinsky, 2016). Empathy played an important role in delivering quality education. It acts as a guide for school culture to create a basis for school organizational designs with empathy as the main ingredient (Debarshi, 2020).

Strategic planning is essential for guiding organizational culture change. The organizational culture influenced the cultural themes on the emergence of organizational structures and programs. Continuous, elaborated, transformed theme categories and definitions provided a practical way of assessing organizational culture change (Wiedman & Martinez, 2017). However, school cultural components like trust and respect among teachers promoted teachers' capacity for organizational learning. Thus, the role of teacher's professional culture in shaping organizational learning capacity is important. In terms of school contexts, the school level was linked to teachers' capacity in two ways. First, as the school level increases, the capacity for organizational learning tends to decrease.

Second, as the school level increases, the positive relation between reflective dialogue and teachers' capacity for learning is weakened (Seashore Louis & Lee, 2016).

The elements of organizational culture that influenced the implementation of school-based interventions included an organizational response to limited resources, the value placed on staff training and professional development, internal support, organizational values, and school climate (Fair, Solari Williams, Warren, Lisako, & Ory, 2018). Also, the principals' values predicted organizational culture and vice versa. The principals focused on two types of values: Druze values such as telling the truth, preserving traditions, and upholding the honor and dignity of others. Organizational culture incorporated universal values such as respect, order, loyalty, inclusion and understanding of others, fairness, flexibility, belonging, commitment, the equation of giving and taking, affiliation, and the importance of the group (Kheir-Faddul, Bibu, & Nastase, 2019). When the principals planned, shaped, or changed the schools' culture, they also successfully managed it (Eger & Prášilová, 2020).

Teachers reported a strong collaborative culture because they had adequate materials and a sense of physical safety. A school can act as a critical and interdependent lever for school change. The positive correlation between teachers' and students' perspectives on the work environment affected it (Weiner & Higgins, 2017). Due to differences in higher education systems, management styles, organizational structure, and organizational behaviors, two universities in North and South Cyprus had distinct personalities. Schools who submitted to accreditations internationally, collaborated with other schools and universities, and offered dual programs have improved teachers's satisfactions and enjoyed success in the programs (Hale Özgüt & Silman, 2018).

A school's overall and organizational health are critical factors in achieving a healthy school. The most important aspects of a healthy school are educational leadership, teacher attitude, school culture, organizational commitment, teacher citizenship behavior, job satisfaction, educational achievement, and students' overall health (Hale Özgüt & Silman, 2018). As a result, self-development necessitates that schools implement the model and make changes based on what is and is not learned. Unfortunately, instructional leadership and school culture are low in Pakistan, while school effectiveness is moderate. In contrast, the correlation between these variables was strong and significant. As a result, school cultures created by educational leaders can contribute to school development and productivity at no additional cost (Ali, 2017).

Organizational culture is a significant predictor of work engagement among government school teachers. There was a significant relationship between organizational culture and job satisfaction. The organizational behaviors, values, and patterns have a significant impact on teachers' levels of engagement in their work (Khan) (2016 Employees' levels of work engagement and affective organizational commitment were interdependent in a school organization.

School leaders gain a better understanding of the importance of leadership culture by taking on more responsibilities and having more faith in themselves and others. They also went out of their way to help and inspire their subordinates to do their best. They also went out of their way to help and inspire their subordinates to do their best. They also went out of their way to help and inspire their subordinates to do their best. The staff also recognized the significance of vision, mission, and values. They have a positive attitude and value themselves and others. They tried out new and creative teaching methods, project-based learning, and parental involvement activities (Soe & Villavicencio, 2017). The school staff also worked with other schools to change the organizational culture while improving student performance (Briody et al., 2018).

Distributed leadership entails responsibilities shared with related skills and expertise. Additionally, empowerment for each member in carrying out one's role may also help maintain school culture. Almost 67% of the observed variance in learning culture in the schools can be explained through leadership and empowerment (Bashir, Akram, Lodhi, 2017). Thus, quality school leadership ensures that teachers provide effective instruction and that the principal provides effective management. Regardless of the principal's leadership style, all actions were directed toward high organizational quality. When there was a lack of consistency in leadership styles, principals found it difficult to implement. As a result, school leaders must be consistent in using the appropriate style based on their personality and the organization's types. (Urlick, 2016).

The organization relies heavily on the leadership of principals. His actions may be advantageous or disadvantageous to the organization. As a result, the principal should have insight and plans for carrying out the organization and appropriate knowledge and leadership skills (Vekeman, Devos, & Valcke, 2016). In addition, leadership entails upholding morals and values, even if it means engaging in subversive behavior to achieve inclusive, equitable, and just outcomes (Wang, 2018).

All principals can contribute and support schools' resources (DeMatthews, Billingsley, McLeskey, & Sharma, 2020). To ensure the safety of resources, school leaders must effectively manage resources and other school facilities. The tasks should be designed to meet the needs of the school or organization. Both teachers and principals have to collaborate to achieve the common goals and outcomes of the organizations (Urlick, 2016). The principals' characteristics enabled them to meet her contextual challenges. While successful principals draw from a similar repertoire of core practices, they enact these core practices in response to their unique contexts to achieve success (Noman, Hashim, & Shaik-Abdullah, 2017). Leadership practices and trust in colleagues had a positive impact on professional learning communities. The leader was also mediated by colleagues' trust (Zheng, Yin, Liu, & Ke, 2016).

School principals have to do teachers' classroom observation and monitoring. They should keep themselves updated as to how their teachers will be evaluated. They

have to adjust their approach to classroom observation based on the new standards and criteria. They also delegate some tasks to other teachers and other school heads to give them more time for in-class observation. They may also collaborate with other teachers in school to help them deliver their tasks as to helping the teachers especially coaching, implement new evaluation practices (Lochmiller & Mancinelli, 2019). The practice enables school leaders to develop teachers, build the capacity of individuals in leadership roles, foster a culture of trust, and foster opportunities for interaction and collaboration among teachers (Nawab & Muhammad, 2020).

School leaders should delegate authority to teachers in order to maximize each individual's potential, which will eventually lead to school improvement through internal initiatives. Distributed leadership should be incorporated into professional development programs for school leaders and teachers (Nawab & Muhammad, 2020). School district administrators should consider changing practices by looking at the organizations' weakest areas and monitoring and evaluating the said practices. Specifically, school leaders may also consider shifting teachers' assignments on a rotation basis to see the improvement or contribution in the organization (Aas & Paulsen, 2019).

The leadership practices of principals that contribute to improving teacher performance are related to ensuring teachers' work and professional development. The principal's practice should lead to attaining the school's teaching goals and improvement of student outputs and activities, or even performance. In practice, school administrators are more likely to participate in school teaching goals than in those relating to teachers' work in the classroom. As a result, good school leadership is more effective than teaching in mobilizing teachers' attitudes and professional practices (Javiera & Pascual, 2018).

Professional learning communities are widely recognized as an effective school improvement strategy for improving student performance and increasing teachers' professional capacity (Zheng, Yin, Liu, & Ke, 2016). Professional development activities include strategies that contribute to the leadership practices of principals, especially those school principals who are not adequately prepared for principalship positions (Gumus & Bellibaş, 2020). They need to develop a human agency and utilize the students' nature and intelligence to impact their academic success (Viloria, 2019) positively. Increased demands on school principals result in high attrition rates among school leaders. A unique university-school collaboration that collaborated on action-based, community-engaged research assisted in addressing the tasks that principals face on a daily basis. The complex roles that school principals play daily may be differentiated if actions are researched based. Leaders from different schools and districts can collaborate to improve school leadership (Van Vooren, 2018).

Schools should prioritize equity framing as the foundation for principal support and leadership development (Rigby, Emily, Boten, Deno, Harrison, Merrell, Seaman, 2019). To respond appropriately to the challenges that may

arise, school leaders must fully integrate the knowledge and skills they learned in many ways (du Plessis, 2017). Equitable Principal leadership practices were varied. Framing objectives are the basic foundation of an organizations' success (Rigby, Emily, Boten, Deno, Harrison, Merrell, Seaman, 2019). Schools can reorient principals as to leadership strategies and actions. As a result, while social leadership in schools is both culturally and pedagogically inclusive, as well as socially distinct (Szeto & Annie Yan, 2018).

The identities of school principals influence their daily leadership practice. However, certain factors associated with their living and working environments appeared to be influencing the personal values embedded throughout their identities (Kafa & Pashiardis, 2019). The regional state must train principals and supervisors to be ready for all challenges (Kelkay, 2020). Principals discussed teacher supervision and the various ways in which they actively monitored the quality of instruction and learning in their schools. Some of the responsibilities and activities of a principal are similar to instructional leadership practices. Hence, proper training for school leaders is a must (Harris, Jones, Lee Cheah, Devadason, & Adams, 2017).

The more principals participate in professional development activities such as professional networking, mentoring, and research, the more frequently they engage in instructional leadership practices. Professional development aimed at getting principals involved in more instructional leadership practices should be based on the new type of professional development activities (Gumus & Bellibas, 2016).

The success of the curriculum guidelines depends on the competent leadership of principals. Guiding teachers in implementing competency-based teaching and enhancing the student's learning effectiveness was one of the important tasks of principals (Wu, Wang, & Lin, 2019). Making instructional leadership a requirement in schools is a worthwhile strategy that can assist teachers in developing a stronger sense of classroom management, instruction, and student engagement (Bellibas & Liu, 2017). Principals were able to significantly improve instructional leadership by delegating leadership tasks on instructional issues to teachers and other non-leaders (Aas & Paulsen, 2019).

The desire for principals to acquire a rural lens as a strategy for improving leadership has significant implications for their initial preparation and ongoing professional development (du Plessis, 2017). The failure of principals to take on leadership roles in transforming school culture is blamed for educational quality issues. Therefore, authorities should equip school principals with knowledge about leadership and its implementation (Adillo & Netshitangani, 2019).

Effective charter school instructional leaders, according to teacher leaders, (a) use diverse communication styles with all stakeholders, (b) promote professional capacity, (c) use diverse data to inform instructional practices and decisions, (d) have a visual and resounding

vision statement, and (e) maximize and preserve instructional time for teachers with few daily interruptions (Davis, & Boudreaux, 2019). In addition, Khumalo (2018) identified five components of transformational leadership, namely sharing of vision, being motivated, committed, and satisfied.

Job satisfaction is regarded as one of the most important factors in job success, as it contributes to an individual's efficiency and comfort (Mirzaii, Riazi, Vares & Alamgard, 2014). It has a strong link to psychological factors. A person who is happy with his job will be emotionally adaptable and enjoy his work (Mirzaii, Riazi, Vares, Alamgard, 2014). Motivated teachers tended to be more satisfied with the job. Motivation is significantly correlated with a willingness to stay with a job.

Demotivation, on the other hand, had a significant negative relationship with the desire to stay on the job (Asgari, Rad, & Chinaveh, 2017). Teachers at six universities in Shenyang, China, were moderately satisfied with their jobs. The strongest relationship between job satisfaction and perceived organizational support in a school culture was discovered (Pan, Shen, Liu, Yang, & Wang, 2015).

Job satisfaction has a significant impact on whether teachers are eager to help others enter the profession (England, 2016). The spirituality of teachers and intrinsic job satisfaction have a meaningful positive relationship. Spirituality is closely related to overall job satisfaction among elementary school teachers (Forsythe, 2016). High school teachers were the most satisfied with their jobs, and middle school teachers were the least confident in their teaching positions. Those with 11 to 15 years of teaching expressed the highest satisfaction levels, and teachers with more than 20 years of teaching showed the lowest job satisfaction levels (Churchwell, 2016).

Job satisfaction is important for job success because it leads to increased efficiency and intrinsic satisfaction in individuals. Factors such as adaptability, job motivation, and job success all have an impact on job satisfaction (Mirzaii, Riazi, Vares, Alamgard, 2014). Satisfied teachers have emotional adaptability and satisfactory enjoyment (Mirzaii, Riazi, Vares, Alamgard, 2014). This contrasts with excellent teachers' satisfaction levels, which were low in terms of "personal growth" and "supervision" (Amzat, Don, Fauzee, Hussin, Raman, 2017).

The satisfaction of teachers is a vital issue in education since it can influence instruction and student outcomes. Therefore, managers and practitioners responsible for monitoring and supporting faculty teaching should be concerned with the level of satisfaction encountered by faculty (Bolliger, Inan, & Wasilik, 2014). Teachers are more likely to be satisfied if they receive appropriate training and if their jobs allow them to work around their schedules. Furthermore, when institutional support and organizational policies support the teaching effort, faculty members are more satisfied (Stickney, Bento, Aggarwal, & Adlakha, 2019). They were, however, dissatisfied with the

technological difficulties as well as the lack of face-to-face interaction and student involvement (Wasilik, & Bolliger, 2009).

Teachers' satisfaction rises when the functional and potential benefits of the learning environment, such as convenience, flexibility, and the potential value of providing accessible learning opportunities, are present (Nagy, 2018); and when the teaching process, which includes course design, development, delivery, and student assessment, is monitored and in place. Teachers' satisfaction is most influenced by perceived usefulness and service quality (Almarashdeh, 2016). Different forms of collaborative activities have different learning effects, and, thus, the design of collaborative learning is important for success. If the learning tasks are properly structured, teachers feel at ease in the teaching-learning process, thus, give them a feeling of satisfaction (Yang, Ghislandi, & Dellantonio, 2018).

Faculty satisfaction is considered a significant quality factor in the organization. The social presence of teachers can be associated with enhanced teaching satisfaction, commitment, accomplishment, and the teacher's expectations of learners (Oyarzun, Barreto, & Conklin, 2018). Individual readiness and satisfaction showed a significant relationship, and readiness predicted satisfaction positively (Adnan, 2018). Some teachers are satisfied with their teaching (Marasi, Jones, & Parker, 2020). Support resources are important for increasing the overall satisfaction of faculty (Meseguer-Martinez, Ros-Galvez, & Rosa-Garcia, 2017). Administrators must find ways to increase faculty satisfaction with teaching in order to improve instruction quality and increase teachers' commitment (Marasi, Jones, & Parker, 2020).

Teachers in Southern Tulare County, California, report moderate to high levels of job satisfaction at their respective schools. Teacher job satisfaction has a direct impact on teacher retention, instructional performance, positive school climate, and student achievement (Stoll-Lollis, 2015). Middle school teachers were the least satisfied with their teaching positions, while high school teachers were satisfied with their job. The years of teaching experience indicated that job satisfaction perceptions change as the years of teaching experience increase. Those with 11 to 15 years of teaching expressed the highest satisfaction levels, and teachers with 20+ years of teaching expressed the lowest job satisfaction levels (Churchwell, 2016).

Teacher development, welfare, motivation, and satisfaction are all important factors in improving teaching performance in a school organization. The result found that excellent teachers were dissatisfied with their personal growth and supervision (Amzat, Don, Fauzee, Hussin, Raman, 2017). Thus, school organizations need to focus on giving the teachers the chance to grow professionally by enrolling in graduate courses or attending webinars and conferences. An innovative school culture has a positive impact on teachers' knowledge sharing and work engagement, as well as the outcome variable, teachers'

knowledge creation practices, and teacher satisfaction (Song, Kim, Chai, & Bae, 2014).

In Delhi, teachers' job satisfaction was average (Tahir & Sajid, 2014). In Southern Tulare County, California, the teachers were moderately satisfied with their job. However, teacher job satisfaction impacts their retention (Stoll-Lollis, 2015). In Turkey, teachers experienced high-level job satisfaction. However, they become less satisfied when their workloads increase (Yerdelen, Sungur, & Klassen, 2016). Professional community and collaboration are predictors of satisfaction, and they also have interactive influences (Stearns et al., 2015). As a result, policymakers and principals must work together to create a positive organizational environment and maintain teachers' job satisfaction in order to improve school quality (Ghavifekr & Pillai, 2016).

In the Philippines, Batangas educators had high level of satisfaction with the hygiene and environment where they worked (Javier & Deligero, 2014). Most of the satisfied teachers with their teaching were female employees who agreed that practices should concentrate on establishing clear goals, encouraging innovation for organizational effectiveness, and achieving continuous improvement through a quality management system (Kalaw, 2014).

Leadership and support from the organization positively affected job satisfaction and life satisfaction, and job satisfaction positively affected life satisfaction (Bachtiar, Sudibjo, & Bernarto, 2018). The schools' leadership style and job satisfaction were related variables. There was no significant difference in the leadership styles of male and female principals; however, when it comes to job satisfaction, male teachers are less satisfied than female teachers (Nazim, & Mahmood, 2018).

Being an employee of a certain organization, it is necessary to look into the variables on organizational culture, leadership practices of the principal which may contribute to the teachers' satisfaction in the job. Hence, this research determined the relationship between the employees' organizational culture and principal leadership practices in relation to the teachers' job satisfaction. Data gathered from this study would be utilized to recommend policies and programs that might contribute to the satisfaction and retention of teachers in the Department of Education.

The study looked into the influence of organizational culture, and principals' leadership practices on the teachers' job satisfaction. Specifically, the study sought answers to the following objectives:

- Determine the schools' organizational culture in terms of dominant characteristics, organizational leadership, management of employees, organizational glue, strategic emphasis, and criteria of success as perceived by the teachers and the school principal;
- Determine the leadership practices of the principal in the areas of modelling the way, inspiring a shared vision, challenging the process, enabling others to act, and

encouraging the heart as perceived by the teachers and the school principal;

- Assess the level of job satisfaction of the teachers in terms of supervision factor, colleague factor, working conditions factor, pay factor, responsibility factor, work itself factor, advancement factor, security factor, and recognition factor;
- Explore significant relationships between the schools’ organizational culture and the teachers’ level of job satisfaction; ;
- Explore significant relationships between the principals’ leadership practices and the teachers’ level of job satisfaction;
- Identify which among the variables in the schools’ organizational culture predict/s the teachers’ level of job satisfaction; and
- Identify which among the variables in the schools’ organizational culture predict/s the teachers’ level of job satisfaction

II. METHODS

This quantitative study made use of the descriptive – correlational design. The goal of descriptive research is to describe a phenomenon and its characteristics. On the other hand, correlational methods often rely on statistical control to rule out the effects of extraneous variables, provide more accurate estimates of relationships among variables, or produce conservative tests of hypotheses (Becker et al., 2016). This design was considered suitable for the present study in determining the effect of schools’ organizational culture and principals’ leadership practices on the teachers’ level of job satisfaction.

The current study was conducted in the three neighboring districts of the Zamboanga del Norte Division. Sindangan North District is located in the northern part of Sindangan. This district comprised 23 elementary schools with 243 teachers and 23 school heads headed by one full-fledged district supervisor. Bacungan District was a lone district before it was divided into two districts, located in Leon B. Postigo, Province of Zamboanga del Norte. There were 20 elementary school with 230 teachers, 20 school heads, of whom three were principals, and one district supervisor. Salug 1 district was one of the two districts of the municipality of Salug, province of Zamboanga del Norte. It comprised of nine schools, including one big Central School with two principals. The district comprised of 120 teachers with ten school heads and a district supervisor.

The respondents of this study consisted of 54 principals from the three districts, chosen through total enumeration. The researcher chose two hundred thirty-three teachers from the three districts through simple random sampling. Only those teachers who have more than two years of experience in teaching and those who gave their full consent were included in the study.

This study used the following instruments:

- A. Organizational Culture Assessment Instrument (OCAI). It is a 24-item questionnaire with six constructs, adapted and modified from Suderzman (2012), and was designed to measure the organizational culture in schools. Responses were rated using a four-point scale ranging from (4 -Totally Agree) to never (1-Totally Disagree). Three experts were given the questionnaire to decide whether to retain, revise, or reject the test items. It was then pilot-tested to school heads who were not included as respondents. The result yielded a Cronbach’s Alpha of reliability coefficient of 0.84 indicating validity and reliability of the instrument.

To determine the school organizational culture, the following continuum was used

Responses	Continuum	Interpretation
4- Totally Agree	3.25-4.0	Very Good (VG)
3- Agree	2.50 - 3.24	Good (G)
2- Disagree	1.75 - 2.49	Fair (F)
1-Totally Disagree	1.0 - 1.74	Poor (F)

- A. Leadership Practices Inventory (LPI). The researcher used this survey instrument to gather the data on the principals’ leadership practices. It is a 30-item questionnaire with five constructs, adapted and modified from Kouzes and Posner (2003). Responses were rated using a four-point scale ranging from (4- always) to (1-never). Three experts were given the questionnaire to decide whether to retain, revise, or reject the test items. It was then pilot-tested to school heads who were not included as respondents. The result yielded a Cronbach’s Alpha of reliability coefficient of 0.79 which indicated that the instrument was valid and reliable.

To determine the school organizational culture, the following continuum was used:

Responses	Continuum	Interpretation
4- Totally Agree	3.25-4.0	Very Good (VG)
3- Agree	2.50 - 3.24	Good (G)
2- Disagree	1.75 - 2.49	Fair (F)
1-Totally Disagree	1.0 - 1.74	Poor (F)

- C. Teacher Job Satisfaction Survey Questionnaire (TJSQ). It consists of 62 items with nine constructs adapted and modified from Lester (1987) to assess teachers’ job satisfaction. Responses were solicited using a four-point scale ranging from 4 (always) to never (1). Five experts validated the tool to decide whether to keep, revise, or reject the indicators. Following that, the expert corrections were incorporated into the final draft. It was then pilot-tested to teachers who were not included as the respondents of the study. The Cronbach’s alpha coefficient was 0.86. Hence it was valid and reliable.

To determine the teacher’s level of job satisfaction, the following continuum was used:

Responses	Continuum	Interpretation
4- Always	3.25-4.0	Very Highly Satisfied
3- Often	2.50 - 3.24	Highly Satisfied
2- Rarely	1.75 - 2.49	Less Satisfied
1- Never	1.0 - 1.74	Not Satisfied

Before the data gathering process began, the researcher obtained a certification from the Graduate School of Misamis University attesting to the approval of the study. This is followed by sending a letter seeking approval from the Schools Division Superintendent in the Division of Zamboanga del Norte to conduct the study in the three districts in the division of Zamboanga del Norte. The researcher also asked permission to survey the District Supervisors of the three districts and the school heads of the elementary schools included in the research. The researcher then personally administered the instruments to the respondents to ensure the fast retrieval of data. The data gathered were tallied using Excel software, presented through tables, and analyzed using the Minitab software. The interpretation of the statistical data followed.

To uphold the ethical aspect of this study, the researcher solicited the voluntary participation of the respondents. The safety of the respondents was taken as the first consideration in conducting the study. The researcher prioritized respect for the respondents’ dignity. She ensured the protection of the privacy of the respondents, an adequate level of confidentiality of the research data, and the anonymity of individuals participating in the research. Moreover, she avoided deception and exaggeration about the aims and objectives of the study; she declared that there are no affiliations in any form, no sources of funding, and any possible conflicts of interest. Finally, any communication about the research was done with honesty and transparency, and avoided any misleading information and misinterpretations of primary data findings. The researcher asked the respondents to sign the informed consent as proof of their willingness to participate.

With the use of Minitab software, the researcher used the following statistical tools in analyzing the data of this study:

Mean and the *Standard Deviation* was utilized in determining schools’ organizational culture, principals’ leadership practices, and teachers’ level of job satisfaction;

Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient was utilized in exploring the significant relationship between the schools’ organizational culture and principals’ leadership practices with teachers’ level of job satisfaction.

Stepwise Regression Analysis was utilized in identifying which among the schools’ organizational culture and principals’ leadership practices predict singly or in combination to the teachers’ level of job satisfaction.

III. FINDINGS

A. Schools’ Organizational Culture

The researcher identified the organizational culture of the schools under study in terms of dominant characteristics, organizational leadership, management of employees, organizational glue, strategic emphasis, and criteria of success as perceived by the teachers and the school principals (Table 1). Both the teachers and their principals have very good ratings of the overall organizational culture of their schools (M= 3.74, SD = 0.29).

Constructs	Teachers		Principal		Overall	
	M	SD	M	SD	M	SD
Dominant characteristics	3.51	0.49	3.99	0.03	3.75	0.26
Organizational leadership	3.54	0.49	3.89	0.12	3.72	0.31
Management of employees	3.54	0.48	3.99	0.08	3.77	0.28
Organizational glue	3.51	0.51	3.83	0.13	3.67	0.32
Strategic emphasis	3.59	0.51	3.99	0.03	3.79	0.51
Criteria of success	3.54	0.51	4.0	0.05	3.77	0.28
Overall	3.54	0.50	3.95	0.08	3.74	0.29

Table 1. Schools’ Organizational Culture
 Note: Scale: 3.25-4.0 (Very Good); 2.50-3.24 (Good); 1.74-2.49(Fair); 1.0-1.74 (Poor)

B. Leadership Practices of School Principals

The culture of the schools is built around the leadership practices of the school principals. In the schools under study, the leadership practices of principals were described in terms of modeling the way, inspiring a shared vision, challenging the process, enabling others to act, and encouraging the heart as perceived by the teachers and the school principals (Table 2). Data revealed that the teachers’ responses (M=3.59; SD=0.57) confirmed the principals’ very good rating of their leadership practices (M=3.99; SD=0.12). Both teachers and principals have very good ratings (M=3.79; SD= 0.35) and had a shared understanding of how their schools are run by their immediate school heads and what directions and performance level they wanted their schools to achieve.

Constructs	Teachers		Principal		Overall	
	M	SD	M	SD	M	SD
1. Modelling the Way	3.63	0.56	3.99	0.38	3.81	0.47
2. Inspiring a Shared Vision	3.56	0.54	3.98	0.07	3.77	0.31
3. Challenging the Process	3.60	0.55	3.99	0.06	3.76	0.34
4. Enabling others to Act	3.54	0.59	3.98	0.08	3.80	0.33
5. Encouraging the Heart	3.60	0.63	3.99	0.03	3.79	0.35
Overall	3.59	0.57	3.99	0.12	3.79	0.35

Table 2 Leadership Practices of Principals
 Note: Scale: 3.25-4.0 (Very Good); 2.50-3.24 (Good); 1.74-2.49(Fair); 1.0-1.74 (Poor)

C. Teachers' Level of Job Satisfaction

Data in Table 3 reveal that the teachers had a very high level of satisfaction with their job (M=3.41; SD= 0.75). It means that the teachers were very highly satisfied with supervision, colleagues, working conditions, pay, responsibility, work itself, advancement, and recognition. However, teachers were satisfied with the security factor (M=2.78; SD = 0.99) of their job. In terms of security of tenure, the teachers still had feelings of losing the job, which they said they could not avoid. Though the teaching profession ensures lifetime security of the family's financial coffers, they had still in their mind the feeling of insecurity sometimes, especially if they fail to follow policies, rules, and regulations in the school and were reminded by their principals.

Constructs	M	SD	Remarks
1. Supervision factor	3.41	0.85	Very Highly Satisfied
2. Colleague factor	3.52	0.61	Very Highly Satisfied
3. Working condition factor	3.45	0.65	Very Highly Satisfied
4. Pay factor	3.36	0.68	Very Highly Satisfied
5. Responsibility factor	3.68	1.21	Very Highly Satisfied
6. Work itself factor	3.62	0.50	Very Highly Satisfied
7. Advancement factor	3.55	0.59	Very Highly Satisfied
8. Security factor	2.78	0.99	Highly Satisfied
9. Recognition factor	3.33	0.69	Very Highly Satisfied
Overall Satisfaction	3.41	0.75	Very Highly Satisfied

Table 3 Teachers' Level of Job Satisfaction
 Note: Scale: 3.25-4.0 (Very Highly Satisfied); 2.50-3.24 (Highly Satisfied); 1.74-2.49(Satisfied); 1.0-1.74 (Less Satisfied)

D. Significant Relationship Between the Schools' Organizational Culture and the Teachers' Level of Satisfaction

Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient was used to test the significant relationship between the school's organizational culture and the teachers' level of satisfaction (Table 4). There was a highly significant relationship between culture of the organization in terms of dominant characteristics and teachers' satisfaction in terms of supervision (r=0.25; p=0.00); colleague (r=0.14; p=0.03);

working condition (r=0.24; p = 0.00); and pay ((r=0.24; p = 0.00) factors of teachers. The organizational glue was highly and significantly related to working condition (r= 0.20, p = 0.00); and working condition (r=0.20; p = 0.00) with teachers' level of satisfaction. The school's strategic emphasis was highly related to pay factor (r = 0.18; p = 0.01).

However, there was a highly significant relationship between culture of the organization in terms of dominant characteristics and teachers' satisfaction in terms of security (r=0.13; p = 0.05); and colleague (r=0.14; p=0.03). The organizational leadership also was significantly related to the teachers' level of satisfaction in terms of security (r = 0.15; p = 0.03). Also, the school's strategic emphasis was related to the teachers' level of satisfaction in the area of supervision (r= 0.15; p = 0.02). The school' criteria of success was also related to the satisfaction of teachers in terms of colleague (r=0.15; p = 0.02); and pay factor (r=0.15; p = 0.02).

Schools' Organizational Culture	Teachers' Level of Job Satisfaction									
	Super vision r(p)	Colleague (p)	Working Condition r(p)	pay(p)	Responsibility r(p)	Work itself r(p)	Advancement r(p)	Security r(p)	Recognition r(p)	
1. Dominant characteristics	0.25 (0.00)**	0.14 (0.03)*	0.24 (0.00)**	0.24 (0.00)**	0.02 (0.71)	0.11 (0.10)	0.04 (0.52)	0.13* (0.05)	0.11 (0.10)	
2. Organizational leadership	0.09 (0.17)	0.05 (0.99)	0.07 (0.29)	0.07 (0.29)	0.03 (0.62)	0.01 (0.87)	0.05 (0.48)	0.15* (0.03)	0.02 (0.97)	
3. Management of employees	0.10 (0.12)	0.02 (0.76)	0.09 (0.16)	0.09 (0.16)	0.01 (0.91)	0.04 (0.57)	0.01 (0.84)	0.13 (0.14)	0.05 (0.48)	
4. Organizational glue	0.17 (0.08)	0.12 (0.07)	0.20 (0.00)**	0.20 (0.00)**	0.03 (0.62)	0.12 (0.07)	0.04 (0.54)	0.09 (0.19)	0.09 (0.19)	
5. Strategic emphasis	0.15 (0.02)*	0.16 (0.01)	0.09 (0.17)	0.18 (0.01)*	0.04 (0.60)	0.05 (0.44)	0.02 (0.71)	0.10 (0.12)	0.09 (0.17)	
6. Criteria of success	0.11 (0.09)	0.15 (0.02)*	0.08 (0.21)	0.15 (0.02)*	0.02 (0.78)	0.06 (0.33)	0.04 (0.57)	0.14 (0.04)	0.06 (0.37)	

Table 4 Significant Relationship between the Schools' Organizational Culture and the Teachers' Level of Satisfaction

Note: ** means highly significant at .01 level; * means significant at 0.05 level

E. Significant Relationship Between the Significant Relationship between the Principal's Leadership Practices and the Teachers' Level of Job Satisfaction

Data in Table 5 revealed that the principals' leadership practices of modeling the way have a significant relationship with the teachers' level of job satisfaction in matters of pay (r = 0.13; p = 0.05). However, the rest of the principals' leadership practices were not significantly related to the teachers' level of job satisfaction as seen in the p-values, greater than 0.05.

Principals' Leadership Practices	Teachers' Level Of Job Satisfaction								
	Super vision r(p)	Chllleague(p) r(p)	Working Condition r(p)	pay(p) r(p)	responsibility r(p)	Work itself r(p)	hancement r(p)	security	cognition
Modelling the Way	0.12 (0.08)	0.09 (0.16)	0.11 (0.11)	0.13 (0.05)*	0.03 (0.65)	0.10 (0.17)	0.06 (0.35)	0.01 (0.90)	0.06 (0.35)
Inspiring a Shared Vision	0.09 (0.19)	0.09 (0.18)	0.05 (0.44)	0.08 (0.23)	0.04 (0.51)	0.08 (0.26)	0.04 (0.55)	0.01 (0.83)	0.05 (0.41)
Challenging the Process	0.10 (0.12)	0.10 (0.13)	0.05 (0.48)	0.11 (0.11)	0.05 (0.48)	0.08 (0.26)	0.04 (0.59)	0.03 (0.61)	0.07 (0.31)
Enabling others to Act	0.10 (0.12)	0.09 (0.16)	0.07 (0.30)	0.12 (0.06)	0.05 (0.48)	0.05 (0.45)	0.03 (0.68)	0.05 (0.68)	0.38 (0.57)
Encouraging the Heart	0.05 (0.47)	0.09 (0.19)	0.09 (0.17)	0.07 (0.23)	0.04 (0.50)	0.10 (0.13)	0.07 (0.29)	0.03 (0.97)	0.02 (0.74)

Table 4. Significant Relationship Between the Principal's Leadership Practices and the Teachers' Level of Job Satisfaction

Note: ** means highly significant at .01 level; * means significant at 0.05 level

F. Regression Analysis on the Schools' Organizational Culture That Predicts Teachers' Level of Job Satisfaction

Simple regression analyses were utilized to determine which of the schools' organizational culture predicts the teachers' level of job satisfaction (Table 5). Data revealed that the schools' dominant characteristics ($\beta = 0.24$; $t=2.04$, $p= 0.04$); and the organizational leadership ($\beta = 0.23$; $t=1.92$, $p= 0.05$) were found to be the predictors of the teachers' level of job satisfaction. Other schools' organizational cultures did not predict the teachers' job satisfaction.

The regression equation (Overall Satisfaction = 4.12 + 0.24 Dominant Characteristics + 0.23 Organizational Leadership) indicates that the unit increase of the schools' organizational culture in terms of dominant characteristics and organizational leadership also increased the teachers' satisfaction by 0.24 and 0.23, respectively. The data indicate that the teachers' job satisfaction can be attributed to the schools' dominant characteristics and organizational leadership. The entire structure of the mentoring, facilitating, and nurturing leadership in the school organization contributed to the teachers' job satisfaction.

The variation of teachers' satisfaction is explained by school culture's dominant characteristics and organizational leadership ($r^2 = 49.70\%$). It means that 49.70 percent of the teachers' job satisfaction is attributed to the overall structure or characteristics and the leadership style practices in a certain school or organization. However, the remaining 49.30 percent was attributed to other factors not included in the study. Hence, another similar study may be conducted for future researchers to examine the other factors that might affect the teachers' job satisfaction.

Predictors	Coef (β)	SE Coef	T- Value	P- Value
(Constant)	4.12	0.27	15.54	0.00
1. Dominant characteristics	0.24	0.12	2.04*	0.04
2. Organizational leadership	0.23	0.12	1.92*	0.05

$R^2 = 49.70$
Dependent Variable: Teachers' Satisfaction
 Overall Satisfaction = satisfaction = 4.12 + 0.24 Dominant characteristics + 0.23 Organizational Leadership

Table 5 Simple Regression Analysis on the schools' organizational culture that predicts teachers' level of job satisfaction

Note : ** means $p < 0.01$ (Highly Significant) at 0.01 level

G. Regression Analysis On The The Principals' Leadership Practices That Predict/S The Teachers' Level Of Job Satisfaction

Data in Table 7 reveal that the only significant factor of the principals' leadership practices that predict or influence teachers' job satisfaction is that of encouraging the heart ($\beta = 0.27$; $t=0.32$, $p= 0.01$). However, the other constructs in the principals' leadership practices did not attribute to the teachers' level of job satisfaction. It indicates that the principal's social competence plays a significant role in maintaining a satisfying relationship in the workplace. It is very heartwarming when the teachers are acknowledged and appreciated in the work that they do and when they get the support they need from their principal and receive expert care and training. There is that intangible feeling of contentment and joy in knowing that they are cared for as individual organization members. Teachers respond productively to new challenges when they are free to choose and decide how to do their work.

The regression equation (Overall Satisfaction = 4.12 + 0.27 encourage the heart) indicates that the unit increase of the principals' leadership practices in encouraging the heart increased the teachers' satisfaction by 0.27. The data indicate that the principal is the central figure in the heart of the school. The teachers respond to the observable manifestations of his expressed emotions through facial expressions, gestures, posture, intonation accompanying emotion, and displayed affection. The teachers, in turn, are satisfied with the job entrusted to them and are secured in the knowledge that the warm and friendly atmosphere in the workplace is the essence of job satisfaction.

The teachers' satisfaction is explained by the principals' encouraging the teachers ($r^2 = 50.61\%$). It means that 50.61 percent of the teachers' job satisfaction is attributed to the practices of the principal in encouraging the teachers to succeed in their way. However, the remaining 49.39 percent may be attributed to other factors not included in the study. Another similar study may be conducted for future researchers to examine the other factors that might affect the teachers' job satisfaction.

Predictors	Coef (β)	SE Coef	T- Value	P-Value
(Constant)	4.12	0.2	17.42	0.00
1. Encouraging the Heart	0.27	0.08	0.32**	0.01

$R^2 = 50.61$

Dependent Variable: Teachers' Satisfaction

Overall Satisfaction = satisfaction = $4.12 + 0.27 \text{Encourage the Heart}$

Table 7 Stepwise Regression Analysis on the the principals' leadership practices that predict/s the teachers' level of job satisfaction

Note : ** means $p < 0.01$ (Highly Significant) at 0.01 level

IV. DISCUSSIONS

The data indicate that the teachers and the principals considered the school a dynamic place of day-to-day enterprises. The schools are a very personalized place impacting the characteristics of the principal and articulated by their teachers in their work. Everybody takes risks and is willing to give his/her share in getting the job done. Wherever the principal wants his school to be, the teachers know their roles in achieving the desired goals. Since the organization is highly controlled and structured, everyone in the organization is aware that he/she is governed by certain procedures in how things are done. Every member of the organization gets his fair share of the work done and ensures positive results. The teachers are aware that the developments and the changing roles are brought about by their leaders' constant mentoring, nurturing, and facilitating their needs. The school leadership is sanctioned by multifarious planning, organizing, coordinating, innovating, and results-oriented focusing.

The findings also indicate that both the school leaders and the teachers used management style of teamwork, consensus, and participation. Without this freedom to innovate or be unique without being indifferent, the work in the school would not harmonize with the goal of the organization. The school has a culture built around the values, which serves as the glue that keeps the organization together. Mutual trust with each other in the organization brings respect to individual talents and skills. The schools also have an effective organization structure that emphasizes strategic planning in both human and material resources.

Additionally, the school leadership puts high trust and openness with their teachers. When teachers are recognized for their individual and collective worth in the organization, they become a productive and creative member of the organization and enjoy the challenges that may arise in the workplace. To complement the development of the human resources in schools, the emphasis of the organization is the acquisition of material resources to meet new challenges, trying out new things and perk the teachers' values and inherent talents and capabilities and use these to the advantage of the organization. The teachers' very good responses to the culture of the Department of Education stemmed from the assurance that there is no permanence and stability of the professions was due to the control and smooth operations of the organization.

School leaders are expected to create an organizational culture to ensure individual capacities in school (Burhanuddin, 2019). The organizational culture shows the power of cultural themes in guiding the emergence of organizational structures and programs (Wiedman & Martinez, 2017). Integration of values, leadership values, and apprenticeship to apply character values into the institutional vision strengthens the school organizational culture and improves school achievement (Imron, Juharyanto, Mustiningsih, & Ahmad, 2018). The findings of this study supported Kalkan Ümit, Altınay, Ramazan, & Gökmen (2020), who said that teachers have a strong or very good perception of school culture. In a school culture, self-development is necessary, which means that schools should apply the model intended for the organization and make changes based on what is learned and not necessarily. School cultures developed can contribute to school development and productivity without extra cost (Ali, 2017).

The principals or school heads shall bring out the best in every organization to develop the teachers' loyalty and high commitment to the organization. Developing the winning spirit of achievement and goal accomplishment and ensuring that the rules and policies of the organization are not violated would surely keep the work of the teachers and the principals running smoothly. He should inspire a shared vision of the school to the teachers to instill in them the idea that they are working towards the same goal to agree on the same standards and principles to arrive at the same end. With this in mind, the teachers are not forced or compelled to work on some things they did not agree on or did not have any knowledge about.

The very good ratings given by the teachers and the school heads imply a mutual recognition that the accomplishments of their schools are a product of collaborative tasks and not singly by the leader. The leader's job is to define the work to be done but gives the teachers the freedom and choice in how they can contribute to the realization of the goals. The teachers see in their leaders the drive for the teachers to grow in their professional endeavors by encouraging them to learn new skills, explore other options without fear of censure, and develop themselves professionally. School leaders were not remiss in acknowledging and celebrating accomplishments and supporting the teachers' contributions.

Effective school leadership between teachers and principals around the schools or instruction influenced each other (Urick, 2016). Principals' leadership has evolved into an activity in which they challenge and disrupt the status quo, as well as oppose policies and practices that are detrimental to their work (Vekeman, Devos, & Valcke, 2016). Leadership entails morals and values, even if it entails employing practices to ensure inclusive, equitable, and just outcomes (Wang, 2018).

One way of developing the principal's leadership practices is through professional development. The more principals participate in professional development activities such as professional networking, mentoring, and research, the more frequently they engage in leadership practices. The

type of professional development should be based on an assessment of the principals' training needs in order for them to carry out their roles and responsibilities in schools effectively. (Gumus and Bellibas, 2016)

The principals have to set the example of what he wants the school to be in its aesthetic value. For the schools to achieve their goals, the principal works as a team to make plans with the teachers, thereby inspiring confidence in their abilities. School heads should take the risks of failure in any endeavor as command responsibility and not blame the teachers entirely. Good leaders embrace a common vision that are shared by every teacher and every staff in their schools and publicly recognize the role of the external stakeholders who have exemplified their commitment to the challenges of fulfilling their roles as school leaders.

The challenge of school heads lies in their sincerity in responding to the commitments they make to the teachers. They should respect the individuality and the uniqueness of each member of the teaching force. They should ensure that the teachers receive their fair share of creative rewards for the success of the projects or attaining excellent results in accomplishing their goals.

The data indicate that while teachers had only a high level of satisfaction in the security of their job and they were sometimes unsure about the stability of their job, they were very highly satisfied with all the remaining factors. The teachers felt a very high level of satisfaction in their job in supervision, colleagues, working condition, pay, and responsibility, work itself, advancement, and recognition. The teachers felt a sense of worth in the organization. They have a constant appreciation of their work because they support each other regarding their personal and professional concerns. In addition, they have their school principal who ensures that harmony and accord are maintained in the workplace. They also expressed greater job satisfaction when the physical surroundings are pleasant. Psychologically, teachers feel that they are part of an organization when the school head defines and communicates his expectations to them.

The teachers in the Department of Education are aware that compensation of teachers is prescribed, and the pay increase is based on merit and rank. They received uniform salaries which teachers need to accumulate points based on performance and merits to get higher salary grades. With the length of time in teaching, they have already internalized the responsibility that accrues with teaching. Teaching inspired teachers as they interact with their pupils and learning from their experiences and about their families. So teachers adhered to the policies of the school and became accountable for their actions. They were also encouraged to enroll in advanced degrees and attend seminars and training to upgrade their teaching field. They received monetary and non-monetary forms of recognition based on their performances on the job. All of these contribute to their very high level of satisfaction.

Every organization requires the transformation of employee behavior into organizational citizenship behavior (Arumi, Aldrin, & Murti, 2019). It means that if an organization shows its employees that it cares and supports them, they will develop an obligated sense of belonging and help the organization achieve its goals (Wiseman, Ngirande & Sam, 2017). Stoll-Lollis (2015) found that teachers in Southern Tulare County, California, had moderately high to high levels of job satisfaction, which contradicted the findings of this study. Teachers in Turkey also report high levels of job satisfaction (Yerdelen, Sungur, & Klassen, 2016). This means that the study of the other countries mentioned earlier in this study is superseded by the teachers' very high level of satisfaction. Teachers must be encouraged to develop intrinsic motivation, self-determination motivation, and interjected motivation, which principals must continue to encourage. These variables were significantly related to teachers' willingness to stay with a job. Extrinsic motivation, integrative motivation, and demotivation, on the other hand, had a significant negative relationship with a desire to stay on the job (Asgari, Rad, & Chinaveh, 2017).

One of the reasons for professionals to prefer teaching is the security of tenure. Since security is the only factor in teachers' job satisfaction where teachers are highly satisfied, school heads have to give assurance to assure that once they are in the DepEd in the teaching profession, there is a lifetime security of the family's financial coffers. Teachers are guided by their heads that for as long as they do not infract the organizations' policies, rules, and regulations and maintain excellence in their work, there is no fear of losing the job.

Data reveal that the factors influencing the teachers' feelings about their job significantly relate to certain aspects of the organization's culture. When the principal can transmit knowledge, exercise high intellectual and aesthetic behavioral characteristics, the teachers can imbibe these traits and share the same in the workplace. Culture in the workplace is built around the way of life shared by the people or place, or time, making teaching satisfying. The data showed that the dominant characteristics of the school are significant at 0.05 level of significance to the satisfaction of the teachers in their job. The school shapes their behavioral characteristics, social practices, and way of life in matters of collegiality and pay. A highly significant relationship was also revealed between the culture of organizational glue and working conditions and pay. Job satisfaction of the teachers is experienced and felt when their intellectual and moral faculties are harnessed. They stick together because of the school's shared attitude, goals, values, and practices and because the principal provides them expert care and training.

The organizational leadership of the principals is significant in ensuring teachers of their security both in the present conditions and the future. Strategic emphasis were significant for the teachers' satisfaction in the supervisory practices of principals. In like manner, they acknowledge that success criteria are articulated in the monetary incentives they receive.

The data finding aligns with how the organizational culture impacts employee retention (Anitha & Begum, 2016). Organizational culture is a predictor of government school teachers' work engagement. The roles, behaviors, values, and patterns manifested in the organization play an important and vital role for teachers who are highly engaged in their work (Khan, 2016). A positive work environment is important in predicting employee satisfaction and retention (Kundu & Lata, 2017).

Organizations must redesign mentoring support and work environment on retention strategies (Aruna & Anitha, 2015). Fair compensation should be considered to have a strong relationship with participation supervision relations (Mutsuddi, 2016). Training and development, teaching empowerment which the organization could extend to teachers, may help. Organizations must pay attention to these influencing factors to help teachers maintain their level of satisfaction while also retaining their key talents (Worku, 2018).

The teachers' level of satisfaction regarding supervision, colleague, working conditions, pay, and security is related to the school's culture and how the organization is structured, led, held, and run. The points of emphasis are set and placed. Hence, school heads need to ensure that the organized school is properly structured that considers formal procedures to govern all the members of the organizations. They have to promote activities like mentoring, facilitating, and nurturing rather than directing the members on what to do in the organization—ensuring that mutual trust, commitment, and loyalty are maintained to have a smooth-running organization.

The teachers can better articulate the organization's goals if the principal sets the example in what he expects from his teachers. The teachers can produce better outputs when the expectations are defined for them and when they are exposed to future trends and their role in realizing these expectations. The principal who paves the way for teachers to meet the challenges and the opportunities for higher pay can stimulate the teachers. Their pay has extrinsic value for the teachers, but it also tests their abilities and builds a natural or intrinsic motivation in achieving the institution's goals.

Principals who practice strategic leadership promote teacher commitment (Khumalo, 2018) and job satisfaction (Hale Özgit & Silman, 2018). The practice promotes distributed leadership by developing a vision for teacher development, strengthening the capacity of individuals in leadership roles, fostering a culture of trust, and creating opportunities for interaction and collaboration among teachers (Nawab & Muhammad, 2020). Fair compensation of teachers had a strong relationship with their participation in the supervision relations of the principals (Mutsuddi, 2016).

The teachers' level of satisfaction is related to how the principals act as role models in the organization. Therefore, school principals have to walk their talk. Whatever they want to expect from their teachers, principals need to

practice or show to the organizations. School heads need to involve the teachers in the planning, implementation and to monitor the curriculum to give teachers empowerment, which in turn develops their positive relationships. By these, teachers may become happy and contented with their status and salary that they receive.

The work engagement of government school teachers is predicted by organizational culture (Khan, 2016). School culture and organizational commitment are the important dimensions of teachers' job satisfaction (Hale Özgit, & Silman, 2018). The principal's personal characteristics, as well as her ability to form strong coalitions, enabled her to meet her contextual challenges in the organizations. 2017; Noman, Hashim, & Shaik-Abdullah). Professional community, collaboration, and teacher control are all predictors of satisfaction that interact with one another. (Stearns et al., 2015; Banerjee et al., 2015; Moller et al., 2015; Mickelson et al., 2015). Every principal has the ability to help create and support schools (DeMatthews, Billingsley, McLeskey, & Sharma, 2020). Regardless of the degree of shared leadership, principals should be held accountable for the school's resources, safety, and facilities. These tasks address fundamental school needs while also contributing to teachers' contentment in the classroom.

Policymakers and school heads may provide a positive organizational environment by considering the organization's structure and ensuring that all the policies are put into the procedure's manual. They may utilize the Plan-Do-Check-Act (PDCA) principle to enhance the quality of the schools' organization. Teachers may use it as their reference as they do their teaching job, which can up-keep teachers' job satisfaction.

The teachers' satisfaction is explained by the principals' encouraging the teachers ($r^2 = 50.61\%$). It means that 50.61 percent of the teachers' job satisfaction is attributed to the practices of the principal in encouraging the teachers to succeed in their way. However, the remaining 49.39 percent may be attributed to other factors not included in the study. Another similar study may be conducted for future researchers to examine the other factors that might affect the teachers' job satisfaction.

The teachers' level of job satisfaction is attributed to how the principals encourage each member, like the teacher, to perform their best and grow in their jobs. More than the principal-directed tasks of facilitating a mission, supervising instruction, and building community, the principal and teacher work as a team and support each other's matters in shared instructional leadership (Urick, 2016). Leadership practices and trust in colleagues had a positive impact on teachers' professional learning communities, including a shared sense of purpose, collaborative activity, a collective focus on student learning, deprived practice, and reflective dialogue (Zheng, Yin, Liu, & Ke, 2016).

School principals should have an attitude of encouraging teachers rather than advising or telling them on things to do. They include teachers in planning, implementing, monitoring the organization. Both groups

have to find ways to celebrate accomplishments simultaneously, share their experiences in taking risks; even when failures strike. Conducting strategic planning and team-building activities may help them build consensus around a common set of values in deciding how to carry their tasks and at the same time run the organization or school.

V. CONCLUSIONS

The perception of a very good school's organizational culture is an acknowledgment of the long years of stay of public school teachers in the Department Education. Organizational culture is built on accumulated values, leadership behaviors, experiences, ways of thinking, new curricula, and organizational expectations. Principals' leadership practices impact shared organizational success, instructional quality, and teachers' psychological and emotional stimulation. Overall, the teachers maintain a very high satisfaction level in their job because of their understanding and acceptance of the dominant characteristics of the culture, organizational leadership of the educational institution they are connected with, and the support, encouragements, and appreciation they receive from the Department of Education..

On the strength of the findings and conclusions resultant from the study, the following recommendations are apparent. The school principals and the teachers further enhance their partnership in sustaining the curricular programs of their respective schools. The principals provide challenging opportunities open to all their teachers regardless of their limitations or strengths. Principals conduct collaborative activities that would enhance teachers' participation in the vision desired for their respective schools. They continue to challenge the teachers to discover their talents, inspiring them to action. They also provide their teachers' logistic support that will lessen the financial burden in preparing teaching materials. Furthermore, the principals maintain a fair share of rewards in the collective success of the programs of the schools. The school principals may also consider making representations to enhance the pay scheme of teachers that the researcher saw to be a strong motivating factor for satisfaction in the workplace.

Teachers continue the positive relationship among the colleagues and provide support to each other to achieve a high level of performance, resulting in high-level satisfaction. The teachers themselves continue with the positive relationship they have with the principals and the healthy working environment to deliver effective instruction. Future researchers may also research the other milieus of excellent job satisfaction among public school teachers.

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